

Punjab/Delhi, India

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Indic Religious Traditions, Vedic Traditions

Vedic Hinduism.

Date Range: 750 BCE - 250 BCE

Region: Punjab & Delhi, India

Region tags: India, Pakistan, Punjab, Delhi, Haryana

Punjab Region, India.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Size and Structure

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, it would seem from the Vedic canon that there were recognized religious specialists exist. The textual tradition appears to show the participation of both religious specialists and patrons. Robust participation of a non-elite section may be less evident.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Punjab/Delhi, India

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)